

Determination of penicillamine in an unsegmented continuous flow analyzer

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Abstract

A kinetic spectrophotometric method for the determination of penicillamine (PEN) in pharmaceuticals has been developed. It utilizes a one-step reduction of the Cu(II)-bathocuproine complex by PEN, which results in a yellow-orange-colored Cu(I)-bathocuproine complex with maximum absorbance at 483 nm. Under optimal conditions, the method is characterized by a linear calibration range of 3.0×10^{-6} – 6.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ ($A_{max} = 8.65 \times 10^3 C_{PEN}$; $R^2 = 1.00$), a limit of detection of 9.0×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹, and an analysis time of 2 min. Using an unsegmented continuous flow analyzer, it has been established that in the linear calibration range, the analytical reaction is of pseudo-first order. The method has been applied to the determination of PEN in samples of pharmaceutical PEN tablets, and the results obtained have been found to be statistically indistinguishable from those produced by the standard Pharmacopoeia method.

Keywords

penicillamine, kinetic spectrophotometry, bathocuproine

Introduction

D-Penicillamine (PEN, 3-mercapto-D-valine, Fig. 1) is a stable non-physiological amino acid containing an SH group and belonging to the aminothiols family (Bjorklund et al. 2020). It is derived from the hydrolytic degradation of penicillin but has no antibiotic effect (Joyce 1990). PEN forms water-soluble complexes with heavy metals and is therefore used as a chelating agent in the treatment of lead, mercury, and arsenic poisoning and for the excretion of copper in the treatment of Wilson's disease (Lawson et al. 2016; Bjorklund et al. 2020). Another medical application of PEN is as a rheumatoid arthritis drug (Joyce

1990; Aaseth et al. 2015). PEN is absorbed well by the gastrointestinal tract, which allows its oral administration (Lawson et al. 2016; Bjorklund et al. 2020).

PEN is used as the active ingredient of pharmaceuticals, the manufacturing of which to the required standards necessitates the use of sensitive, selective, inexpensive, and rapid methods for PEN determination.

The British Pharmacopoeia recommends acid-base titration in non-aqueous media for the determination of PEN (British Pharmacopoeia 2018). However, a number of studies have been focused on the development of alternative methods for the quantitative determination of this sulfur-containing compound in pharmaceutical and

Figure 1. Structural formulas of 3-mercapto-D-valine (PEN), neocuproine and bathocuproine disulfonic acid (BCS).

biological samples. These methods involve a variety of detection techniques, including spectrophotometry with color redox and complexometric reactions (Besada et al. 1989; Al-Majed 1999; Walash et al. 2003; Walash et al. 2004; Martinović et al. 2007; Skowron and Ciesielski 2011; Naik et al. 2013; Agarwal et al. 2016; Kukoc-Modun et al. 2021; Srivastava 2021), voltammetry (Raouf et al. 2009), potentiometry (Radić et al. 2000; Martinović and Radić 2007, 2009), amperometry (Torriero et al. 2007), fluorimetry (Al-Majed 2000), chromatography (Cao et al. 2018), and atomic absorption spectrometry (Bramanti et al. 2008). Spectrophotometry is commonly used in pharmaceutical analysis for quality control due to its simplicity, availability, and low cost. Some of the spectrophotometric methods for PEN determination used a kinetic approach (Walash et al. 2003; Walash et al. 2004; Martinović et al. 2007; Naik et al. 2013; Agarwal et al. 2016; Kukoc-Modun et al. 2021; Srivastava 2021). Kinetic methods have increased in popularity in pharmaceutical analysis because, in most cases, they offer improved selectivity by minimizing the effect of the sample matrix, and, in addition, they provide valuable kinetic information about the analytical reaction (Crouch et al. 1998; Kukoc-Modun et al. 2017). However, the kinetic methods for the determination of PEN suffer from drawbacks such as the use of toxic (i.e., Hg) (Agarwal et al. 2016; Srivastava 2021) or unstable (i.e., azide) (Walash et al. 2003) reagents, a low sampling rate (i.e., 10–20 min per analysis) (Walash et al. 2004; Martinović et al. 2007; Agarwal et al. 2016; Srivastava 2021), significantly lower sensitivity than the other kinetic methods (Naik et al. 2013), and a narrow working pH range (Kukoc-Modun et al. 2021).

In an earlier study, PEN was determined by a one-step redox color reaction (Eq. (1)) of PEN with the Cu(II) complex with neocuproine (NCN) (Fig. 1) (Kukoc-Modun et al. 2021). However, in subsequent studies involving the determination of *N*-acetyl-L-cysteine ethyl ester, another drug with reducing properties like PEN, by both NCN and its derivative, bathocuproine disulfonic acid (BCS) (Fig. 1), it was established that BCS provided higher sensitivity than NCN (Kukoc-Modun et al. 2017; Kukoc-Modun et al. 2024).

It can be expected that similarly to *N*-acetyl-L-cysteine ethyl ester, the stoichiometry of the reaction of PEN with BCS (Eq. (2)) will be analogous to that with NCN (Eq. (1)).

where RSH represents PEN with its thiol group (SH).

The stable orange-colored $[\text{Cu}(\text{BCS})_2]^{3-}$ complex has an absorption maximum at 483 nm (Kukoc-Modun et al. 2017).

The present paper describes the development, optimization, and validation of a kinetic spectrophotometric method for the determination of PEN, which uses the single-step redox color reaction between PEN and the Cu(II)–BCS complex ($[\text{Cu}(\text{BCS})_2]^{2-}$) and overcomes the drawbacks of the kinetic methods mentioned above. In addition, it outlines the kinetic characteristics of the color analytical reaction used in this study.

Materials and methods

Reagents and solutions

All reagents were of analytical grade and were used without further purification. Milli-Q water (Milli-Q, Millipore, USA, 18 M Ω) was used for solution preparation.

The Britton-Robinson buffer solution (4.0 \times 10⁻² mol L⁻¹; pH = 2) was prepared by dissolving 4.95 g boric acid (Kemika, Croatia), 4.79 g glacial acetic acid (VWR Chemicals, France), and 5.45 g orthophosphoric acid (Kemika, Croatia) in 2.0 L of Milli-Q water. The pH value was adjusted by adding a 2.0 mol L⁻¹ solution of sodium hydroxide (Kemika, Croatia) while monitoring the solution pH.

Acetate buffer solutions (pH = 3.5–4.5) were prepared by mixing appropriate volumes of 0.5 mol L⁻¹ sodium acetate (Kemika, Croatia) and 0.5 mol L⁻¹ acetic acid (Kemika, Croatia) solutions. The pH was adjusted by adding a 2.0 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide solution.

A stock solution of 8.0 \times 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ Cu(II) was prepared by dissolving 99.9 mg CuSO₄·5H₂O (Kemika, Croatia) in 50.0 mL Milli-Q water.

A 2.0 \times 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ solution of bathocuproine disulfonic acid (BCS) was prepared by dissolving 56.5 mg of bathocuproine disodium salt (Alfa Aesar, Karlsruhe, Germany) in 50.0 mL of Milli-Q water.

A $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ stock solution of PEN was prepared by dissolving 0.1492 g PEN (Fluka Chemika, Buch, Switzerland) in 100 mL Britton-Robinson buffer solution (pH = 2) and stored at 4 °C in a dark bottle to ensure its stability for at least 30 days. Working standards were prepared daily by diluting the above stock solutions with Milli-Q water.

A perchloric acid solution was prepared and standardized for the titrimetric analysis of the pharmaceutical samples in accordance with the British Pharmacopoeia procedure (British Pharmacopoeia 2018).

Apparatus and procedure

All pH measurements were conducted with a pH meter (SevenMulti, Mettler Toledo, Switzerland) equipped with a combined glass electrode (InLab[®]413, Mettler Toledo, Switzerland).

All kinetic measurements were performed in a closed-configuration unsegmented continuous flow analyzer for continuous sample introduction, shown in Fig. 2.

Such analyzers are characterized by unsegmented flow and continuous introduction of samples as a flowing stream at a low flow rate. They are suitable for monitoring evolving systems such as the kinetics of the reaction between PEN and the $[\text{Cu}(\text{BCS})_2]^{2-}$ complex. The analyzer consisted of a peristaltic pump (IPC, Ismatec, Switzerland) for continuously propelling the reaction solution, which was located in a thermostated, jacketed reaction vessel and mechanically mixed using a magnetic stirrer. The components of the analyzer were connected by PTFE tubing (0.8 mm i.d.). The absorbance of the Cu(I)-BCS complex, produced in the reaction vessel, was monitored in time at 483 nm in the flow-through cuvette (160 μL internal volume and 10 mm optical pathlength, Hellma, USA) of a UV/Vis spectrophotometer (UV-1601, Shimadzu, Japan) connected to a laptop running Hyper UV-Vis software (Shimadzu, Japan). The recorded kinetic data, with a frequency of 1 s per reading, were then transferred to GraphPad Prism Ver.

4.03 for Windows (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA) for curve-fitting, regression, and statistical analysis. A thermostat bath with a digital thermoregulator (Julabo, Germany) was used to circulate water at a preselected temperature through the jacketed compartment of the reaction vessel to maintain the reaction solution at the desired temperature.

Acetate buffer (10 mL, pH = 5.0), Cu(II) solution (0.45 mL, $8.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), BCS solution (1.80 mL, $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), and 1.75 mL of Milli-Q water were added to the thermostated jacketed reaction vessel under continuous stirring. The resultant reaction solution was recirculated through the flow-through cuvette of the analyzer for 1 min at a constant flow rate of 6 mL min^{-1} before the analytical reaction was initiated by adding 1.0 mL of PEN standard solution, thus bringing the total reaction solution volume to 15.0 mL.

Interference study

Stock solutions (0.2 mol L^{-1}) containing common inorganic ions (K^+ , Na^+ , NO_3^- , and SO_4^{2-}) and excipients in pharmaceutical formulations were used in the interference study. They were prepared by dissolving KNO_3 , Na_2SO_4 , lactose, D-(+)-glucose, D-(-)-fructose, sodium citrate, citric acid, L-(+)-tartaric acid, and boric acid (Kemika, Croatia) in Milli-Q water. Appropriately buffered solutions containing $4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ PEN and the individual interferents in interferent: PEN molar ratios of 5:1, 10:1, 50:1, 100:1, 250:1, and 500:1 were analyzed.

Validation study

A commercially available pharmaceutical (Metalcaptase tablets, 150 mg PEN per tablet, Heyl, Chemisch-Pharmazeutische Fabrik, GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) was analyzed to validate the newly developed method. The analytical procedure involved the mixing of five tablets in powder form. An amount of powder corresponding to 150 mg PEN (declared amount of PEN per tablet) was dissolved in

Figure 2. Schematic of the closed-configuration unsegmented continuous flow analyzer for studying the kinetics of the analytical reaction used in the determination of PEN.

500 mL of Milli-Q water, and after filtering (blue ribbon filter paper, S&S, Germany), the supernatant was analyzed by both the newly developed method and the British Pharmacopoeia titrimetric method (British Pharmacopoeia 2018).

Recovery studies involved the analysis of tablet samples spiked with 50–200 mg PEN.

Results and discussion

Effect of the analytical reaction parameters

It was established that after the addition of PEN standards to the reaction vessel (Fig. 2), the absorbance of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{BCS})_2]^{3-}$ complex at 483 nm rapidly increased, reaching a plateau in 50 s (Fig. 3). Therefore, it was decided to study the effect of the main analytical reaction (Eq. (2)) parameters (i.e., solution pH and temperature, and Cu(II):BCS and $[\text{Cu}(\text{BCS})_2]^{2-}$:PEN molar ratios) on the absorbance of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{BCS})_2]^{3-}$ complex at 60 s. Taking into account that 60 s were used for achieving a stable baseline signal prior to the standard addition, the actual absorbance value used in the abovementioned study was reached 120 s after the start of the measurement.

Figure 3. Transient absorbance curves at 3 different PEN concentrations. The reaction parameters have the initial values listed in Table 1.

The initial and optimal values of the analytical reaction parameters and the ranges within which they were studied are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Initial and optimal values of the analytical reaction parameters and the corresponding ranges within which they were optimized in the order in which optimization was conducted. The concentration of PEN in the reaction vessel was $4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.

Reaction parameter	Initial value	Examined range	Optimal value
pH	4.0	2.0–8.0	5.0
Temperature / °C	25	10–50	25
[BCS]:[Cu ²⁺]	1.0	0.5–3.0	1.0
[Cu(BCS) ₂] ²⁻ : [PEN]	6.0	2.0–10.0	4.0

When studying the effect of pH using Britton-Robinson buffer, it was found that the absorbance increased from pH 2 to pH 3 and then leveled off. This result allowed the use of acetate buffer at pH 5 in all subsequent experiments, thus avoiding the introduction of borate, a potential interferent, in the reaction mixture when using the Britton-Robinson buffer.

The temperature effect was negligible in the temperature range studied (Table 1), and all subsequent experiments were conducted at room temperature of 25 °C. Therefore, no thermostating was required, thus simplifying the analytical procedure.

It was observed that the absorbance increased when the [BCS]:[Cu²⁺] ratio was increased from 0.5 to 1.0. However, further increase of this ratio up to 3.0 did not produce higher absorbance, and therefore the ratio of 1.0 was selected as the optimal value of this reaction parameter.

The absorbance increased with increasing the reagent to PEN ratio (i.e., [Cu(BCS)₂]²⁻: [PEN]) from 2.0 to 4.0 and then leveled off. Hence, 4.0 was selected as the optimal value of this reaction parameter.

Analytical figures of merit

Under optimal reaction conditions (Table 1), the method is characterized by a linear range of $3.0 \times 10^{-6} - 6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ described by the following calibration equation: $A = 8.65 \times 10^3 [\text{PEN}]$ ($R^2 = 1.000$). The limit of detection (LOD), calculated as 3 × standard deviation of the blank, was found to be $9.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.

Table 2 compares the analytical performance of the newly developed method with existing kinetic spectrophotometric methods for the determination of PEN. As can be seen, the newly developed method offers higher sensitivity

Table 2. Comparison of the analytical performance of kinetic spectrophotometric methods for the determination of PEN in pharmaceutical formulations.

Ref.	Reagents	λ [nm]	Measurement time [min]	Linear range [mol L ⁻¹]	LOD [mol L ⁻¹]
(Walash et al. 2003)	Sodium azide and iodine	348	5	$1.0 \times 10^{-5} - 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	9.4×10^{-7}
(Walash et al. 2004)	Potassium permanganate in alkaline medium	610	20	$1.3 \times 10^{-5} - 6.7 \times 10^{-5}$	1.4×10^{-6}
(Martinović et al. 2007)	Fe(III) and 1,10-phenanthroline and Cu(II)	510	10	$8.0 \times 10^{-6} - 8.0 \times 10^{-5}$	2.5×10^{-6}
(Naik et al. 2013)	$\text{Na}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$	421	5	$1.0 \times 10^{-4} - 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$	2.1×10^{-5}
(Agarwal et al. 2016)	Hg(II), $[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and nitroso-R-salt (NRS)	525	15	$2.9 \times 10^{-6} - 2.7 \times 10^{-5}$	3.0×10^{-7}
(Srivastava 2021)	Hg(II), $[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and pyrazine	370	15	$1.0 \times 10^{-5} - 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	1.0×10^{-6}
(Kukoc-Modun et al. 2021)	Cu(II) and neocuproine	458	2	$1.5 \times 10^{-5} - 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$	3.5×10^{-6}
Present method	Cu(II) and bathocuproine	483	2	$3.0 \times 10^{-6} - 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$	9.0×10^{-7}

than all other methods, except for the method involving the use of Hg^{2+} (Agarwal et al. 2016), which is a highly toxic reagent. The newly developed method and the method utilizing the Cu(II)-neocuproine complex (Kukoc-Modun et al. 2021) provide the widest linear ranges and the shortest measurement time of 2 min; however, the latter method has a higher LOD value. On the basis of the analytical figures of merit presented in Table 2, it can be concluded that the newly developed method offers superior analytical performance over the existing kinetic spectrophotometric methods for the determination of PEN.

Interferences

The influence of possible interfering species that are commonly found in commercial pharmaceutical formulations (excipients) and inorganic salts often present in the reaction solutions was investigated in synthetic solutions containing $4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ PEN and the species studied in large excess. The tolerance limit was defined as the highest interferent: PEN ratio that would still cause an error within $\pm 5\%$. The results of the interference study are shown in Table 3. Taking into account that the tested concentrations of the common excipients listed in Table 3 were much higher than those commonly found in commercial pharmaceuticals, it was concluded that the newly developed method offered the required degree of selectivity for the determination of PEN in common pharmaceutical formulations.

Table 3. Interference effect in the determination of PEN ($4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$).

Interferent	Interferent: PEN	Relative error [%]
Glucose	500 : 1	-0.14
Fructose	500 : 1	+1.02
Lactose	100 : 1	+3.27
Na_2SO_4	100 : 1	+2.68
KNO_3	500 : 1	+1.80
Boric acid	50 : 1	+0.43
Citric acid	100 : 1	+2.86
Tartaric acid	50 : 1	-4.15
Sodium citrate	100 : 1	+2.55

Analytical reaction kinetics

The analytical reaction kinetics was studied under optimal conditions (Table 1) in the closed-configuration unsegmented continuous flow analyzer for continuous sample introduction by measuring the initial reaction rate (V , Eq. (3)) with respect to the PEN concentration in the reaction vessel in the range 2.0×10^{-7} – $4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, where the reagent (i.e., $[\text{Cu}(\text{BCS})_2]^{2+}$) was in sufficiently large excess. It should be noted that this concentration range corresponds to the linear calibration range of PEN.

$$V = \frac{\Delta c}{\Delta t} = \frac{\Delta A}{b \Delta t} = kc^n \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta t = 15 \text{ s}$, b is the slope of the calibration curve ($8.65 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$), k is the kinetic rate constant, and n is the reaction order.

By plotting $\lg V$ versus $\lg c_{\text{PEN}}$ (Fig. 4) and fitting it by Eq. (4), n and $\lg k$ were determined as 1.041 and 5.345, respectively, thus indicating that under optimal conditions and in the PEN concentration range mentioned above, the analytical reaction was of pseudo-first order.

$$\lg V = \lg k + n \lg c \quad (4)$$

Figure 4. Linear plot of $\lg V$ vs. $\lg c_{\text{PEN}}$ obtained under optimal conditions (Table 1) where V and c_{PEN} are the initial reaction rate (Eq. (3)) and the molar concentration of PEN in the range 2.0×10^{-7} – $4.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ respectively.

Validation of the method

The amount of PEN in commercial PEN tablets containing 150 mg PEN per tablet was determined in triplicate by the newly developed method and the reference method (British Pharmacopoeia 2018), and the results were found to be statistically indistinguishable at the 95% confidence level (i.e., $150.8 \pm 0.5 \text{ mg}$ and $147.2 \pm 1.8 \text{ mg}$).

The recovery experiments using the same PEN tablets produced recovery values in the range of 97.4–102.6% (Table 4), thus further confirming the validity of the newly developed method.

Table 4. Evaluation of the accuracy of the newly developed method for the determination of PEN by analyzing solutions of tablet powder corresponding to 150 mg PEN spiked with different amounts of PEN.

Added [mg]	Found \pm standard deviation [mg]	Recovery [%]
0	149.0 ± 0.5	–
50	199.5 ± 0.3	97.40
100	253.4 ± 0.7	102.60
150	304.3 ± 0.8	102.33
200	355.1 ± 1.1	102.15

Conclusion

The newly developed kinetic method for the spectrophotometric determination of PEN in the visible range, which utilizes a one-step redox reaction, is characterized by high selectivity regarding common excipients, a wide linear range (3.0×10^{-6} – 6.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹), a low LOD (9.0×10^{-7} mol L⁻¹), and a short analysis time (2 min), thus exhibiting the best analytical performance among existing kinetic methods for the PEN determination. The analytical reaction involving the reduction of the Cu(II)–bathocuproine complex by PEN was studied in an unsegmented continuous flow analyzer for continuous sample introduction and was found to be of pseudo-first order in the linear calibration concentration range. The kinetic experiments also demonstrated that a constant absorbance value was established 50 s after the start of the analytical reaction and was maintained for at least 5 min, thus allowing a reliable routine spectrophotometric measurement to be carried out in that period. The newly developed method was successfully validated with commercial PEN tablets and recovery experiments, which further supported its suitability for the analysis of PEN in pharmaceutical formulations.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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